

1 **Figure 1.** The proportion of homotypic compared to heterotypic matings recorded during the
 2 female (a), male (b) and group (c) mate choice assay. Female (a,c) and male population identity
 3 is shown on the x-axis. An asterisk represents a significant deviation from a random mating ratio
 4 as indicated by a repeated G-test for goodness of fit ($p < 0.05$).

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6 **Figure 2.** The latency (a,b) and duration (c,d) of matings in the choice assays. Female (a,c) and

7 male (b,d) population identity is shown on the x-axis. Letters indicate significant differences

8 between mating types.

9 **Figure 3.** The hatchability (a), egg to adult viability (b), body weights (c) and average
 10 development time (d) of flies from parental and hybrid crosses. Letters indicate significant
 11 differences between cross identities.

12 **Figure 4.** The average proportion of red eyed offspring produced by flies from parental and
 13 hybrid crosses, in competition with brown eyed competitors. Average proportions were
 14 determined for each replicate population and plotted. The dashed line indicates the expected
 15 proportion of $\frac{1}{3}$ of the offspring. Letters indicate significant differences between cross identities.